

EFFECT OF CARD GAMES AND JIGSAW PUZZLE ON STUDENTS' ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE IN BIOLOGY IN ONNA LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA OF AKWA IBOM STATE

BY

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Abstract

The study examined the effect of card games and jigsaw puzzle on students' academic performance in Biology in Onna Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State. The research design used for the study was quasi-experimental design. It is a pre-test, post-test, control group design. The population of the study consisted about two thousand six hundred and eighty-five (2685) SS2 Biology students. A total of 100 students comprising of fifty (50) male and fifty (50) female were found as sample in the two intact class of the two schools selected for the study. The instrument used for data collection for the study was the Biology Performance Test (BPT) and the instrument consisted of 20 multiple choice questions with four options lettered A-D on Biology concepts drawn from the SS2 Biology scheme of work. The reliability of the instrument was tested using Kuder Richardson KR-21 which yield reliability coefficient of 0.79. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions while independent t-test was used to test the null hypotheses formulated. The findings revealed that there was statistically significant difference between the performance of Biology students taught the concept of respiratory system using card games and jig-saw puzzle teaching strategies. The findings also showed that there is no significant difference in the mean performance scores between male and female biology students taught the concept of respiratory system using card game teaching strategy. Finally, the findings of this study also revealed that there was no significant difference in the mean performance scores of male and female Biology students taught the concept of respiratory system using jigsaw puzzle teaching strategy. It was recommended among others that teachers should use card game and jig-saw puzzle teaching strategies in teaching and learning of respiratory system and other concepts in Biology as these strategies makes learning concepts more significant, easy and meaningful to students and increasing the interest of the students in Biology and construction of a life-long knowledge needed for national development. Card game teaching strategy should be combined with jig-saw puzzle as these strategies facilitates students' involvement in the class work by sharing answers, trying to participate, paying attention, giving the examples, encouraging to take part in the lesson, participating as volunteers, interacting with each other as well as enhancement of cognitive and vocabulary skill development.

Keywords: *Card Games, Jigsaw Puzzle, Academic Performance, Biology*

INTRODUCTION

Biology has to do with the study of living things, their characteristics and interactions with the environment (Michael, 2017). Biology plays important role especially in the explanation of complex life processes, structures, functions, origin, evolution and distribution of living organisms. The knowledge of Biology is needed for national development and global competitiveness in the

area of Medicine, Agriculture and Physical and Health Education, especially in sports and environmental studies among others. The subject is designed to empower students with basic knowledge about the functioning of their body system, inter-relationship between them and other living things and environmental sustainability. In the Biology Curriculum document of Nigerian Educational Research

and Development Council (NERDC) (Federal Republic Nigeria, 2014), it was stipulated that Biology should be taught in a way that will help students acquire adequate and relevant laboratory skills and management in the subject.

In the National Policy on Education (FRN, 2014), Biology comes first under the theme: “Fields of Studies”: in a sub-titled theme: “Science and Mathematics”, followed by Chemistry, Physics, Further Mathematics, Health Education, Agriculture, Physical Education and Computer Studies. A major concern in science teacher education is the development of teachers’ pedagogical content knowledge for improving classroom practice and students learning. Preliminary observation has proven that Biology teachers use conventional method to teach most of the topics in Biology, giving large notes and assignments meant to keep the learners busy without positive impact on their cognition and affection. Education can only be functional if the knowledge acquired is applied to solve problems. In the recent time, education has been given top priority in the affairs of many nations, since the desire of man over the years has been knowledge acquisition (Ogbiji, 2013).

The development of new strategies to affect qualitative teaching and learning of Biology has been the major task of both curriculum developers and the skillful teachers (Kolb, 2019). In this situation, some learners in Biology tend to develop personal approaches to learning. These strategies and approaches have formed the bedrock for good performance in the subject. Schank (2017) explained that Biology students obtain better result in their test when they are allowed to use individual approach to learning by their teachers. This approach aligns with Kolb’s theory in the area of constructive learning model. Effective management of learning for better results

depends on the teacher’s ability to apply suitable strategy or strategies during the teaching process (Cavanagh, 2015).

It was confirmed that Biology students learn better when negative behaviours are minimized and higher level students’ involvement on the learning process are pursued and encouraged. This view is supported by Grouns and Ebsinier (2012) as they assert that active Biology instruction, which involves both the teacher and the students in whichever form will produce high ordered skills and retentive capacity especially when the teacher is professionally and academically trained to employ adequately the relevant teaching models. Other problems associated to poor delivery of Biology instruction as identified include low morale and poor preparation of teachers, overcrowded classroom/inadequacy of laboratory and workshop facilities, poor attitude of students to work, gross under-funding and inadequacy of rewards for excellence in science teaching and learning among others Obomanu & Nbina, (2016). In addition, pieces of research evidence show that Biology teachers are poorly trained in both content knowledge, assessment techniques and pedagogy (Ibe, 2018). Against this background, this research sought to find out the effect of Card Games and jigsaw-puzzle teaching strategies on students’ academic performance in Biology.

Card Game has been widely discussed in recent years. Card game is known for its effectiveness in improving students’ learning motivation, attitude, engagement, and performance (Sailer, Hense, Mayr, & Mandl, 2017; Subhash & Cudney, 2018). In general, Card game refers to the idea of using games for the educational purpose, e.g., serious games (Connolly, Boyle, MacArthur, Hainey, & Boyle, 2012). Another common educational practice is the card game of learning (Seaborn & Fels, 2015), suggesting that teachers apply

game elements and game mechanisms into the learning activities, such as points, competition, and leader board. Antonaci, Dagnino, Ott, Bellotti, Berta, De Gloria, Mayer, (2015) pointed out that applying card games in learning could help the learners become more active and motivated. Many educational card games have been proposed to improve students' learning performance.

Card game according to Kapp (2012) is defined as the use of game design elements, game-play mechanics, aesthetics, and game thinking for non-game applications to motivate students." Although there has not been a universal term for card game, most of them share some standard features. Lately, though, card games has focused to digitally engage students, utilizing platforms or applications with the use of digital devices like tablets, smartphones, or computers. For instance, Cheung and McBride (2017) showed that a special card game for math learning gave children multimodal cues to facilitate their number learning. Also, unplugged games have been implemented for supporting varied learning subjects, e.g., creative thinking (Chung, 2013), ecosystem concepts (Lin & Hou, 2016). Game was considered an effective tool to promote students' motivation and engagement in learning (da Rocha Seixas, Gomes, & de Melo Filho, 2016).

A well-designed card game instructional activity could create a gaming environment for players to interact with the game and other players. In addition, previous studies also suggested that instructors can use the process-oriented approach with games or activities to reduce negative academic emotions (Bruny, 2013). Card game is known to be a key role in the lives of not only humans but also all living things. Games, which are beneficial for different purposes for people of all ages, have fundamental contributions to the education and development of individuals. In this sense, card

games had to be integrated in curricula not only as an entertainment tool but also as an educational tool (Malta, 2018). Card game has a significant place in terms of educational science and it is a real educational tool. However, some societies that attach importance to formal education do not consider it as a productive activity and therefore do not include it in their education systems (Aral, 2017).

Instructional strategy for easy implementation of biology curriculum which embraces affective domain could be jigsaw-puzzle instructional strategy. Kelly (2016) defined jigsaw puzzle as a type of cooperative learning which improves social interactions in learning and supports diversity. The Jigsaw-puzzle is comparable to the work place where each individual is expected to play a role to achieve a common goal. It is a strategy that leaves students as experts and receivers of knowledge. In a jigsaw-puzzle, a teacher divides learning experience into stages or sections. The teacher distributes the sub-topics to individuals in a group. Students from different groups who have the same topic meet together to have groups discussion on the sub-topic allotted for individuals to research their assigned area. Jigsaw-puzzle is one of the strategies that teach peaceful coexistence, human worth and the development of critical thinking and hard work. The strategy could be effective in learning concept such as growth in biology.

Gender is one of the factors that influence students' performance in science in senior secondary schools. It is a concept that calls for research review from time to time. Gender is a psychological term describing behavior and attributes expected of individuals on the basis of being male or female (Umanah, 2017). Gender differences in students' performance have been of great concern to Basic Science educators, yet research findings have been

inconsistent. Some researchers are of the opinion that male students perform academically better than their female students, others found the opposite; on the other hand, other researchers found no differences at all between male and female students' academic performance in Biology. There is therefore the need to use teaching strategies that encourage gender equality, positive interdependence and group work so as to motivate the students for higher academic performance. This strategy encourages male and female participation in group work and in the search for knowledge. The use of card game Jigsaw-puzzle for teaching allows individualization of learning and encourages students to seek out the content they like. Students interact in a traditional classroom with their colleagues in order to learn new lessons. There is therefore a wide gap to be filled which the use of active interactive strategy can take care of. Based on the above, the study focused on the effect of Jigsaw-puzzle teaching strategies on students' academic performance in Biology in Onna local Government Area.

Statement of the Problem

The underperformance of Biology students in West African Senior School Certificate Examination in Nigeria has become a worrisome situation that calls for urgent attention. Chief examiners' report on West African Senior School Certificate Examination (2021) showed that the performance of Biology students in 2021 was slightly poorer with a raw mean score of 31 and standard deviation of 11.92 when compared with the raw mean of score of 31 and the standard deviation of 10.91 of WASSCE 2019. The West African Examination Council (WAEC) Chief Examiner's Report 2013, 2015, 2016, 2017, 2018, 2019, 2021 and 2022 noted that students' performance in Biology is very poor. Students' poor academic performance to some extent is traceable to inappropriate instructional strategies used by the teachers.

Hence, it is based on this that the present study sought to investigate on the effect of card games and jigsaw puzzle on students' academic performance in Biology in Onna Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State.

Research Questions

- i. What differences exist in the mean performance scores of Biology students taught the concept of respiratory system using card games and jigsaw puzzle teaching strategies?
- ii. What differences exist in the mean performance scores of male and female Biology Students taught the concept of respiratory system using card games teaching strategy?
- iii. What differences exist in the mean performance scores of male and female Biology Students taught the concept of respiratory system using jigsaw puzzle teaching strategy?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated to guide the study

- i. There is no significant difference in the mean performance scores of Biology students taught the concept of respiratory system using card games and jigsaw puzzle teaching strategies.
- ii. There is no significant difference in the mean performance scores of male and female Biology students taught the concept of respiratory system using card games teaching strategy.
- iii. There is no significant difference in the mean performance scores of male and female Biology students taught the concept of respiratory system using jigsaw puzzle teaching strategy.

Research Design

The research design for the study was quasi-experimental design. A quasi-experimental design is a type of experimental design that does not provide for full control of extraneous variables, primarily because of the lack of random assignment of subjects to groups.

Methodology

The population for the study consists of all senior secondary school two (SS2) Biology students in Onna Local Government Area. There are nine (9) public senior secondary schools in Onna Local Government Area and a total of 2685 SS2 Biology students (Local Education Committee, 2022). The sample of this study consisted of Senior Secondary School Two (SS2) Biology students drawn from 2 public secondary schools in Onna Local Government Area. In deriving the sample for this study, simple random sampling technique was used. From each of the school selected, 1 school was assigned to science text cards while the other school was assigned to word games.

One SS2 intact class in each of the school was randomly drawn to obtain sample for the study. At the end of the instructional process, all SS2 students found in each of the intact class became sample for the study. A total of 100 students comprising of male and female were found as sample in the two intact class of the two schools selected for the study. Since coeducational schools was used for the study, each gender representation was ensured as each intact class in made up of male and female students.

The instruments that were used for data collection in this study are: Biology Performance Test (CPT) and Lesson plan on Biology using Card Game and Jigsaw puzzle. The instrument consisted of 20 multiple choice questions with four options lettered A-D on Biology concepts drawn from the SS2 Biology scheme of work. The instrument was administered to both the Cards Game group

and Jigsaw puzzle group to measure their academic performance in Biology after the treatment. Two lesson plans were developed by the researcher. One was developed based on Card game and the other one was developed based on Jigsaw puzzle. The two lesson plans were developed on the same concepts in Biology for the same category of students.

To establish the reliability of the instruments, the researcher subjected the instrument for trial test using 20 SS2 students drawn from schools in the area of study. The students that were used for trial testing the instruments were not part of the students sampled for this study. The reliability of the instruments was tested using Kuder Richardson KR-21 reliability estimate. A reliability coefficient of 0.79 was obtained and considered high enough to put the instrument to use for data collection in the study.

The researcher first administered the pretest to the students in the two schools and obtained their scores to ascertain their pre-entry ability before treatment. After the pretesting exercise, the first school was taught using Card game while the second school was taught using Jigsaw puzzle. The two schools were taught the same concepts in Biology. The instructional process lasted for three weeks. After the instructional process, the researcher administered the post-test to the students to test their academic ability after treatment. On completion, the instruments were collected and appropriately parceled for easy identification during scoring and collation. The data generated from the retrieved instruments was analyzed using appropriate statistical tool. Research questions were answered using mean and standard deviation while hypotheses were tested at .05 level of significance using independent t-test.

Result

Research Question 1: What difference exist in the mean performance scores of biology

students taught using the concept of respiratory system using card game and jig-saw puzzle teaching strategies?

Table 1: Mean and standard deviation of mean performance scores of students on pre-test and post-test classified by treatment groups.

Instructional strategies	N	Pretest		Posttest		Mean Gain Scores
		X	SD	X	SD	
Card games	50	35.50	14.68	55.20	15.90	19.70
Jig-saw puzzle	50	34.90	15.00	56.00	16.16	21.10

The result show that the students taught respiratory system taught using card games had post- test, pre-test mean gain of 19.70 and those taught with jig-saw puzzle had 21.10. This observation shows that the students taught using jig-saw puzzle had the best performance.

Research Question 2: What differences exist in the mean performance scores of male and female Biology Students taught the concept of respiratory system using card games teaching strategy

Table 2: Mean and standard deviation of scores between male and female biology students taught respiratory system using card games teaching strategy.

Gender	N	Pretest		Posttest		Mean Gain Scores
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Male	24	34.17	14.79	53.75	15.05	23.28
Female	26	36.73	14.76	56.54	16.83	19.81

The results show that the male and female students taught the concept of respiratory system taught using jig-saw puzzle had post-test – pre-test mean difference of 23.28 and 18.09 respectively.

Research Question 3: What differences exist in the mean performance scores of male and female biology students taught the concept of respiratory system using jig-saw puzzle teaching strategy?

Table 3: Mean and standard deviation of scores between male and female biology students taught respiratory system using jig-saw puzzle teaching strategy

Gender	N	Pretest		Posttest		Mean Gain Scores
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Male	29	35.69	15.85	58.97	17.08	23.28
Female	21	33.81	14.05	51.90	14.18	18.09

The results show that the male and female students taught the concept of respiratory system taught using jig-saw puzzle had

posttest – pre-test mean difference of 23.28 and 18.09 respectively.

Testing the Hypotheses

Hypothesis one: There is no significant difference in the mean performance scores of

Biology students taught the concept of respiratory system using card games and jigsaw puzzle teaching strategies.

Table 4: Independent t-test analysis of Biology students post-test taught the concept of respiratory system using card- games and jig-saw puzzle teaching strategies.

Where s = significant.

Instructional strategies	N	Mean	Sd	Df	t-cal	t-crit	Decision
Crossword	50	55.20	15.90	98	2.49	1.98	S
Flash cards	50	56.00	16.16				

In table 4, the calculated t-value for the main effect of instructional strategies at df 2, 98 is 2.49, while its corresponding t-critical value 1.98, indicate that the instructional strategies used had statistically significant effect on the performance of students in the concept of respiratory system. Hence, Hypothesis 1 (H_{01}) was rejected.

Hypothesis two: There is no significant difference in the mean performance scores of male and female Biology students taught the concept of respiratory system using card games teaching strategy.

Table 5: Independent t-test analysis of male and female Biology students post-test taught the

Gender	n	Mean	Sd	Df	t-cal	t-crit	Decision
Male	24	53.75	15.05	48	.65	2.01	Ns
Female	26	56.54	16.83				

concept of respiratory system using card- games teaching strategy. Where Ns = Not significant

In table 5, the calculated t-value (.65) for the main effect of gender at df 2, $p < .05$ is less than the t-critical value (2.01), indicating that the students' gender had no significant effect on the performance of the students in the concept of respiratory system. Hence, hypothesis was upheld.

Hypothesis three: There is no significant difference in the mean performance scores of male and female Biology students taught the concept of respiratory system using jigsaw puzzle teaching strategy.

Table 6: Independent t-test analysis of male and female Biology student's post-test taught the concept of respiratory system using jig-saw puzzle teaching strategy.

Gender	n	Mean	Sd	Df	t-cal	t-crit	Decision
Male	29	58.97	17.08	48	.66	2.01	Ns
Female	21	51.90	14.18				

Where Ns = Not significant

In table 6, the calculated t-value (.65) for the main effect of gender at df 2, $p < 0.05$ is less

than the t-critical value (2.01), indicating that the students' gender had no significant effect

on the performance of the students in the concept of respiratory system. Hence, hypothesis 3 was upheld.

Discussion of Findings

Hypothesis One: This hypothesis sought to examine the significant difference between the performance of Biology students taught the concept of respiratory system using card games and jig-saw puzzle teaching strategies. The result of findings in this hypothesis revealed that there was statistically significant difference between the performance of Biology students taught the concept of respiratory system using card games and jig-saw puzzle teaching strategies. This result is in line with the assertion made Shu-Ming, Yi-Chen and Cheng (2019) whose findings indicated that students in the card game instructional activity showed better learning performance. Meanwhile, students' math anxiety level was reduced after the card game activity. The findings of the study also support that of Chukwu and Dike (2020) who revealed that the result of the study showed that Jigsaw-Puzzle and Graphic Organizer are effective instructional strategies for enhancement of students' academic performance in growth as a concept in Biology.

Hypothesis Two: This hypothesis state that there is no significant difference in the mean performance scores between male and female biology students taught the concept of respiratory system using card game teaching strategy. The null hypothesis earlier stated was upheld. The result from testing this hypothesis found that there is no significant difference in the mean performance scores between male and female biology students taught the concept of respiratory system using card game teaching strategy. The findings of this study is in support of a similar study conducted by

Cosmas (2023) who showed that there is no significant difference in the mean performance scores between male and female students in biology when taught using crossword puzzle game approach.

Hypothesis Three: Findings from the testing of hypothesis three as shown in table 6 revealed that there was no significant difference in the mean performance scores between male and female biology students taught the concept of respiratory system using jig-saw puzzle teaching strategy. The null hypothesis earlier stated was upheld. This implies that students taught using jig-saw puzzle benefited equally. The finding of this study is in line with the assertion made by Akpochimora (2018) revealed that there was no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of male and female students in urban and rural schools taught chemistry using jig-saw cooperative learning instructional strategy.

Conclusion

The study found that card game and jig-saw puzzle teaching strategies were more effective in the selected concepts in Biology and enhanced the students' academic performance positively. Card game and jig-saw puzzle teaching strategies are gender friendly. Also, there are creative tools whose proper implantation definitely has positive impact on student vocabulary skills and performance.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made based on the findings of the study:

1. Teachers should use of card game and jig-saw puzzle teaching strategies in teaching and learning of respiratory system and other concepts in Biology as these strategies makes learning concepts more significant, easy and meaningful to students and increasing the interest of the students in Biology

and construction of a life-long knowledge needed for national development.

2. Card game teaching strategy should be combined with jig-saw puzzle as these strategies facilitates students' involvement in the class work by sharing answers, trying to participate, paying attention, giving the examples, encouraging to take part in the lesson, participating as volunteers, interacting with each other as well as enhancement of cognitive and vocabulary skill development.

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